

Coherent Point-to-Multipoint Coexistence with 50G-PON for Next-Generation Optical Access

Gaël Simon^{1*}, Fabienne Saliou¹, Alexandre Afonso², Carlos Castro³, Antonio Napoli³, Mokhtar Bouzayani², Franck Bonnafous², Philippe Chanclou¹

¹ Orange, 2 avenue Pierre Marzin, 22307 Lannion, France; ² Infinera, France; ³ Infinera, Munich, Germany

*gael.simon@orange.com

Abstract: We demonstrate the coexistence of a prototype 200 Gb/s symmetrical coherent point-to-multipoint system with a 50G-PON prototype. The optical budget exceeds 35 dB in downstream over the C-Band. The imbalance of the terminations is assessed. © 2024 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of internet users was 6% over the last 5 years [1]. Meanwhile, mobile 5G deployment and coming 6G push forward “fiber-like” experiences (low latency, massive capacity) [2], opening opportunities for the optical access network as a transport solution. To meet those requirements, the International Telecommunication Union (ITU-T) is working on specifications for a 100 Gb/s single-wavelength system to meet Point-to-Point applications. Innovation is also occurring in the field of Point-to-Multipoint (PtMP) optical access, as the ITU-T is consolidating the first version of the Very High Speed PON (VHSP) [3], the successor of 50 Gigabit-capable Passive Optical Network (50G-PON) [4], with the latter already achieving 50 Gb/s in downstream (DS). It is not decided yet if the VHSP will use direct or coherent detection; the transition from legacy direct detection (commonly used in legacy Passive Optical Networks (PONs) systems) to coherent technology is crucial, particularly at higher bitrates where direct detection will face severe limitations.

Certainly, operators will need to reuse the deployed infrastructure, as it is by far the main component of cost in optical access networks. Reuse will require the coexistence of PON generations, and Multi-PON Modules are the most common solution. The PtMP infrastructure will need to meet high Optical Budgets (OBs) (in the range of 14-29 dB for N1 class, and up to 20-35 dB for E2 class), to support a reach of up to 20 km, and a wavelength coexistence with other technologies to allow smooth migration or at least infrastructure sharing. Also, a dynamic range as high as 15 dB can be required between the highest and the lowest Optical Path Loss (OPL) on the same Optical Distribution Network (ODN). In this paper, we assess the ability of a Coherent Point-To-Multipoint (Coherent-PtMP) system designed for metro and long-haul applications [5, 6] to meet the requirements of access networks. We also demonstrate for the first time the coexistence of such a coherent-PtMP prototype with a 50G-PON prototype.

2. Experimental Setup

Figure 1 illustrates the experimental setup. The top left part shows the 50G-PON Optical Line Termination (OLT) prototype described in [7]: the DS operates at 50 Gb/s and 1342.7 nm, while the upstream (US) bitrate is 25 Gb/s and the wavelength 1299.8 nm. The prototype demonstrated optical budgets of 23.9 dB in DS at 50 Gbit/s and 26.9 dB in US at 25 Gbit/s [7]. A Semiconductor Optical Amplifier (SOA), providing 15 dB gain, is used to boost the DS signal and preamplifies the US one, while a pair of fixed attenuators located between the OLT and the SOA protect the OLT receiver from overload and optimizes the OLT working point in the DS. A fixed optical add-drop multiplexer, used as Coexistence Element (CE_x) (1.8 dB insertion loss), mixes the DS 50G-PON signal with the DS Coherent-PtMP, before propagating through 20 km of Standard Single-Mode Fiber (SSMF) and a Variable Optical Attenuator (VOA) (VOA1). Finally, a power splitter distributes the signal to the 50G-PON Optical Network Unit (ONU).

Fig. 1: Experimental setup.

The Coherent-PtMP system, consisting of a “Hub” at the central office side and two “leaves” at the client side, as represented on Figure 1. The Hub and Leafs exploit Frequency Division Multiplexing: 16 Sub-Carriers (SCs)

transport 4 GBaud signals using 16-Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (QAM) on both polarization states. In this way, a gross rate of 32 Gb/s is achievable per SC, leading to a net rate of 25 Gb/s after forward error correction. The 16 SCs can be dynamically allocated to the Hub and Leafs: it is, for example, possible to allocate all SCs in DS, thus providing up to 400 Gb/s [8]. We chose to allocate four SCs per Leaf in DS and four SCs per Leaf in US, providing a global bitrate of 200 Gb/s in both directions (100 Gb/s per Leaf). The Hub acts as a wavelength reference (set to 1544 nm): when the Hub's wavelength drifts (either to meet the wavelength plan requirement, or because of environmental factors), the Leafs follow the drift, relaxing the constraints when demodulating the signal. The system works in C-band, where a few PtMP systems already operate; the DS wavelength of the XGS-PON works in the low L-band, the DS of G-PON in the S-band, while a 10 nm range (1550–1560 nm) may be used for video, see Figure 2).

Fig. 2: Point-to-multipoint systems wavelength plan.

An Erbium-Doped Fiber Amplifier (EDFA) is used in each direction to amplify the Coherent-PtMP signals, as an optical circulator separates and recombines the US and DS. The EDFA gain is set to 15 dB in DS and 18 dB in the DS. A 6 dB attenuator is used in the US to protect the receiver. The Coherent-PtMP shares with the 50G-PON the optical path consisting in the SSMF and VOA1. A second VOA (VOA2) inserted on Leaf 2 assesses the performances when the leafs are unbalanced. The optical spectrum of both the 50G-PON and Coherent-PtMP systems are presented in Figure 3.

3. Results and Discussions

We first assess the performance of the Coherent-PtMP system when not coexisting with the 50G-PON. The percentage of received frames versus received power (measured at the circulator input in the DS and CEX in US) for a 20 km reach are presented in Figure 4. The frames are 1500 Bytes long and the sensitivity limit is achieved when the received packet rate goes below 100%. The DS (Hub to Leaf 2) sensitivity is -25.3 dBm, while the US sensitivities of Leafs 1 and 2 are -23.1 dBm and -24.2 dBm respectively. The DS signal is launched at 13.8 dBm at the CEx input, while the Leafs output powers are 1.2 and 2.0 dBm at the circulator's outputs. Table 1 summarizes the resulting OBs when the signal propagates over 0 km (Back-to-Back (BtB)), 20 km and 40 km. In the DS, the OB is higher than 39.1 dB in all three configurations, exceeding the upper limits of the PON class E2 ODN (35 dB). In the US, Leaf 2 meets the N1 class (29 dB) upper limit in BtB.

Fig. 3: Spectra of 50G-PON: US (a), DS (b); and Coh-PtMP (c)

Fig. 4: Experimental sensitivity measurements of the Coherent-PtMP.

We next focus on the coexistence of the 50G-PON system with the Coherent-PtMP one. The performance of 50G-PON is reported in detail in [7]. It is here captured in terms of the ability of the ONU to remain connected to the OLT while the optical pass losses increase, using the Loss Of Signal alarm, when Coherent-PtMP and

Table 1: Coherent Point-to-Multipoint system Optical Budget (OB) measurements summary

	Tx Power 1544 nm (dBm)	OB BtB 1544 nm (dB)	OB 20 km 1544 nm (dB)	OB 40 km 1544 nm (dB)	OB 20 km 1544 nm w/ 50G-PON (dB)	OB BtB 1567 nm (dB)	OB BtB 1528 nm (dB)
Hub to Leaf	13.8	40.7	39.1	39.6	39.1	37.1	41.6
Leaf1 to Hub	1.2	30.6	26.1	25.6	26.1	31.4	/
Leaf2 to Hub	2.0	31.4	28.0	28.0	28.0	/	29.3

50G-PON share 20 km of fiber, as shown in Figure 5. No significant difference is observed in the 50G-PON performance (the 0.3 dB OB gain in the US by the 50G-PON when coexisting with the Coherent-PtMP is assumed to be a measurement artifact). Similarly, in Table 1, no variation is observed in the OB of the Coherent-PtMP system when coexisting with the 50G-PON. In fact, the wavelength difference between the two systems (O-band for 50G-PON, C-band for Coherent-PtMP) is higher than 200 nm, which is beyond the Stimulated Raman Scattering range in SSMF, while the high input power (+13.8 dBm for the DS Coherent-PtMP at CEx input) does not seem to stimulate another non-linear effect.

The tunability (full C-band, from 1567 nm to 1528 nm) of the Coherent-PtMP system was also assessed. The results, depicted in Table 1, show a similar performance to those at 1544 nm, demonstrating the ability of the Coherent-PtMP to ease the coexistence with already deployed technologies in tuning its carrier over 39 nm (1528–1567 nm) while meeting at least 37.1 dB OB in the DS and 27.5 dB in the US in BtB.

Fig. 5: Impact on 50G-PON of coexistence with the Coherent Point-to-Multipoint system

Fig. 6: Leaf 2 performance when unbalanced OPLs

Apart from achieving high OBs without in-line amplification, the ODNs used for PONs are characterized by a high dynamic range between ONUs: up to a 15 dB difference in OPLs can be observed on the same infrastructure. Leafs 1 and 2 are unbalanced in varying VOA2 attenuation (see Figure 1). The results, summarized in Figure 6, show that a dynamic range of up to 10.0 dB is sustainable with the current version of the Coherent-PtMP.

4. Conclusion

We successfully demonstrated for the first time, to the best of our knowledge, the coexistence of a 50G-PON prototype and a 200 Gb/s coherent point-to-multipoint system for beyond 50G-PON over 20 km of standard fiber. The Coherent-PtMP system achieves up to a 40.7 dB optical budget in the downstream and 30.6 dB in the upstream at 1544 nm in back-to-back, meeting N1 class, while demonstrating a 39 nm optical coherent source tunability.

5. Acknowledgement

We would like to thank ZTE for the loan of the 50G-PON prototype. This work was carried out in OCTA-PUS HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-06 project (number: 101070009). A. Napoli and C. Castro gratefully thank the partial support of the EU project ALLEGRO, G.A.No. 101092766.

References

1. CISCO, "Cisco Annual Internet Report (2018–2023) White Paper." [Online], Available: <https://www.cisco.com>.
2. P. Chanclou et al., "Optical access solutions in support of 5G and beyond [Invited]," in JOCN, July 2023.
3. ITU-T, G.sup.VHSP – PtMP passive optical access system req. above 50 Gbit/s per wavelength (WIP).
4. ITU-T, G.9804.3 (G.hsp.50Gpmd) – Physical Medium Dependent Layer for 50G single Channel PON systems (2021).
5. C. Castro et al., "Scalable filterless coherent point-to-multipoint metro network architecture," in JOCN, May 2023.
6. W. Sande et al., "1800 Km 16QAM Transmission With a 400G QSFP-DD Coherent Pluggable," ECOC 2023, UK.
7. F. Saliou et al., "Coexistence in Future Optical Access Networks from an Operator's Perspective," in JOCN, 2023.
8. A. Rashidinejad et al., "Real-Time Point-to-Multipoint for Coherent Optical Broadcast ..." OFC 2023, San Diego, USA.